

COST ANALYSIS OF GRADUATE PROGRAMS IN UP DILIMAN AND SELECTED
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIS) IN THE PHILIPPINES
OFFERING LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCES: BASIS FOR
MASTER IN ARCHIVES AND RECORDS MANAGEMENT
TUITION FEE POLICY

TIMOTHY JASON C. ABORQUEZ
MARIA VICTORIA YSABEL O. CUCUECO
JOEMER JOHN C. DE VERA
WARREN N. GUTIERREZ
JOSEPH G. ICAONAPO
VHIA LOUWHELLA A. IMPRESO
ANGELYN J. SAGER
ISAIAH GIL E. ORTIZ
CHRISTINE ANNE DA. TAPAN
ROBERTO V. VASQUEZ
HAZEL ROSE L. YAMSON

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LIS 192: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH IN LIS

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Introduction

The University of the Philippines School of Library and Information Studies (UP SLIS) currently offers three (3) graduate programs in pursuing the LIS profession. The School has a Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) with a revised program effective AY 2022-2023. New courses and electives were added to further enrich the theory, specialization, and research components of the degree program (Buenrostro & Santos, 2021). The second program is the thesis option of the MLIS called Master of Science in Library and Information Science (MSLIS). The third and recently approved by the University is the Master in Archives and Records Management (MARM) program. The MARM is a two-year program and is the first of its kind in the country and in the region aiming to provide formal education on archiving and recordkeeping.

The previous graduate program rates in UP SLIS have not changed since then and are priced at 500 pesos per unit. Putting into several factors such as inflation, increasing financial requirements in maintaining quality education, and the need to standardize programs, the School has decided to adjust its graduate program rates at 3,000 pesos per unit for the MARM program.

This study explores and assesses the existing rates of other graduate programs in UP Diliman, comparing with the prospected rates currently set. In addition, existing rates of other universities and colleges in the Philippines that offer LIS graduate education are also analyzed including the factors that influence such rates. The data gathered in this study may provide support in future decision-making conducted by the School in its graduate program rates and offerings.

Review of Related Literature

There are existing studies conducted on the basis of reviewing the tuition fee policies of an institution and its offered course offerings. Ferrer, Hermosisima, and Abulencia (2014) study collected data and information that could be utilized by the policymakers and management of the Philippine Normal University in assessing the efficiency and sustainability of the university of the current tuition policy. Santiago, Ponce, Uy (2004) cost analysis research of degree programs for Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University breaks down and analyzes the financial, student, and faculty information for the calendar year 2001. On a larger scale, Santiago, Largoza, Ponce, Intal, Alba, Rufino's (2002) research on the cost analysis of selected degree programs for selected higher educational institutions in NCR gathers data and information in order to provide a methodology to estimate the student cost.

Valderrama (2005) study presents a methodology in calculating the direct cost of undergraduate instruction at the University of the Philippines which considers the cost of the facilities such as the library holdings, computer, teaching, and research laboratories. The estimation that was used in the study presented findings that the material cost component was 25% of the total direct cost of undergraduate instruction at the said institution. Fast forward,

in the comparison of the University of the Philippines Diliman's OUR Memorandum No. MVPLO 2020-07 and 2021-06, or the Schedule of Fees for the Midyear Term 2020 and 2021, it can be noted that there is not much change in the tuition fees of the graduate programs, especially in UP SLIS.

Studies about tuition fees in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are also a matter of interest in other countries. Sung-Hyun Cha (2013) studies the estimated break-even number of students and return of the investments for human resource development online program, calculating the cost of course development and delivery, as well as revenue from enrolled students between 2013-2032. Czarnecki, Korpi, Nelson (2020) outlined a new approach to the comparative analysis of student finance systems based on social rights which is an approach that is widely used in the areas of social policy. The conclusion of the study shows that student support is less generous in countries that benefit from students of low-income families. Ball (2018) tested if the 2006 increase of tuition fees in England affected the individual choice of students to study STEM degree programs. Results reject this hypothesis and show that a reduction was most likely caused by compositional change. Marcucci & Johnstone (2007) created a comprehensive study regarding tuition fees and their context in politics, finance, and ideology. Wilkins, Shams & Huisman (2013) surveyed the effects of the increasing tuition fees in England on the decision-making process of students seeking higher education. Results suggest that financial issues are a more important factor in the student's choices.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive research design to identify the current nominal tuition rates of graduate programs in UP Diliman and LIS graduate programs in higher education institutions. Miscellaneous fees, other required fees, units required to complete the program, and estimates in terms of enrollees per semester were also identified.

For UP Diliman graduate programs, the dataset was primarily obtained from the Office of the University Registrar Memorandum No. MVPLO 2021-06 with subject "Schedule of Fees for Midyear Term 2021." There are a total of 29 graduate programs in UP Diliman listed in the memorandum. Using box and whisker plots, the dataset displayed summary measures depicting the graduate courses' tuition fee per unit on average.

On the other hand, the dataset for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering Library and Information Science (LIS) graduate programs was retrieved from the Electronic Freedom of Information website or eFOI. It has a list of accredited LIS schools requested from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). There are a total of 39 LIS schools in the dataset. However, no information about tuition fees has been provided. The researchers also obtained data from FindUniversity.ph. The website has information about tuition fees but in terms of the overall cost and in range.

To address the lack of reliable information about tuition fee policies, the researchers employed purposive sampling, surveying both UP Diliman graduate schools and LIS schools through Google Forms. Qualitative questions were added in the survey questionnaire to know any recent adjustments on tuition rates and some possible factors in deciding the tuition rate of the graduate programs.

Participants were college administrators addressed to any of the following: dean, college secretary, and graduate school directors. Data gathering started on the 7th of January and ended on the 17th of the same month. Informed through email, the researchers were able to obtain 12 responses from UP Diliman graduate programs and 5 responses from LIS schools. Dataset of LIS schools was statistically analyzed through bootstrapping. Samples were repeated 100 times and with replacement to infer the confidence intervals.

Lastly, all information collected is subject to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or RA 10173. The datasets are used only for the study itself and are accessible only to the researchers and the MARM administrators.

Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

Graduate Programs in UP Diliman

The box and whisker plot of tuition fees per unit of all graduate courses in Figure 1 shows that the median or the midpoint of the dataset is Php 1,500. This is higher than but a near observation to the actual mean of Php 1,461. The lower quartile is Php 500 while the upper quartile is Php 2,500. The minimum value and maximum value in the dataset are Php 300 and Php 4,500 respectively. There are no outliers in the dataset. Meanwhile, the distribution of the box and whiskers plot appears to be positively skewed or skewed to the right due to above-average tuition rates in M Business Administration and MS in Finance being offered in UP Diliman Bonifacio Global City.

Figure 1. Boxplot distribution of tuition fees/unit of all graduate programs in UP Diliman

In Figure 2, it is shown that tuition fees per unit across the categories of Arts and Letters, Management and Economics, Science and Technology, and Social Sciences and Law range between Php 300 at its lowest to Php 4,500 at its highest. Median values are varying from one another. 62% of graduate programs within UP Diliman indicate that the minimum tuition fee per unit ranges between Php 300 to Php 500. The remaining 38% has a minimum tuition fee per unit of Php 700; these programs are all located within the Science and Technology cluster and with the most varied observations. The Arts and Letters cluster, on the other hand, has the least varied observations. Outliers are present in the Science and Technology cluster and Social Sciences and Law cluster. Skewness for all clusters is very different, with emphasis on the Management and Economics cluster having symmetric distribution.

Figure 2. Boxplot distribution of tuition fees/unit of graduate programs in UP Diliman (cluster)

According to the responses given by the graduate programs within UP Diliman in Table 1, the rationale for their respective program's tuition fee per unit structure along with the various miscellaneous and additional fees can be summarized as follows: the need for facility and laboratory maintenance; the need for facility and technological improvements; inflation and the financial capacity of students; the need to have competitive rates vis-a-vis other postgraduate degree-granting institutions; and lastly, as a matter of compliance with the university policy.

Table 1
Survey Questionnaire Responses from UP Diliman Graduate Programs

Program	Total units	Tuition fee/ Unit	Misc fees	Other fees	Enrollees per sem	Tuition last updated since	Factors in deciding the program's cost
Master of Science in Human Movement Science	39	500	2500 +	N/A	100-120	2012	University policy
Master of Arts in Economics, Master in Development Economics	30	700	1415	7500	40	-	-
Master in Araling Pilipino	33	500	1250	N/A	300	No idea	No idea
Master of Science/Master in Statistics	38, 37	2500	1700	N/A	112	2018	Financial capacity of the students
Master of Industrial Relations	33	2000	3500	N/A	300	2018	Inflation, improvements of facilities, upgrading of technology, financial capacity of students
Master of Fine Arts	39	500	2000	N/A	35-40	2012*	For the Graduate Program as well as the College Executive Board's matters to be discussed
Master of Sociology	36	500	1540.5	N/A	20	-	There should be no charges in the program. It should be free like the bachelor's degree.
Master of Library and Information Science	37, 36	500	1415	78.50	100-200	**	Technological advancements, inflation, increasing demand for LIS professionals
Master of Family Life and Child Development	35-38	2500	1415	608.5	69	2009	Laboratory needs and equipment purchase and maintenance
MS Computer Science	31	1500	1415	***	80	No idea	No idea
Master of Business Administration, Master of Science in Finance	42, 30	4500	1650	N/A	100	2017	Cost of facilities, competitive rates
Master of Islamic Studies	30	300	1200	1498.5	8-10	N/A	financial capacity of students

* Since I was employed in the College in 2010, no tuition fee policy was made. However, in 2012, the office conducted a study on tuition fee increase but did not materialize due to lack of manpower (disorganization of the personnel, limited staff, tasks had to be shouldered by staff that was left in the administrative office).

** The SLIS has not been requested but is currently working on it.

*** Laboratory fee, if any – P 100-1,500.00/per subject; Student Fund – P 46.50/per semester; Entrance Fee (new students only) – P 30.00; Deposit Fee (new students only) – P 100.00; Photo-ID (new students only) – P 130.00; Education Development Fee (Foreign Students only); Non-Resident – \$500.00 per semester; Resident – \$250.00 per semester

Graduate Programs in Select HEIs Offering LIS

Tuition Fee/Year

The histogram in Figure 3 shows that the bootstrap distribution for the annual costs of LIS graduate programs in the Philippines according to FindUniversity.ph appears to be normal. In this result, the estimate for the population mean is approximately Php 18,403. The researchers are 95% confident also that the mean tuition fees per year of LIS graduate programs in the Philippines is approximately between Php 12,800 and Php 24,000.

Summary Statistics for Bootstrap Distribution:

Bootstrap Samples	Statistic	Unique Values	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max
100	Mean	100	18,283	3,046	10,311	16,032	18,068	20,215	25,672

Figure 3. Bootstrapped distribution of tuition fees/year of sampled LIS graduate schools

Figure 4. Confidence interval of tuition fees/year of sampled LIS graduate schools

Tuition Fee/Unit

Meanwhile, the histogram in Figure 5 shows that the bootstrap distribution for the tuition fees per unit of sampled LIS graduate schools from the survey responses appears to be normal. In this result, the estimate for the population mean is approximately Php 850. At 95% confidence level, there is sufficient evidence that the population mean in this case is approximately between Php 600 and Php 11,000.

Summary Statistics for Bootstrap Distribution:

Bootstrap Samples	Statistic	Unique Values	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max
100	Mean	100	852	148	543	740	866	955	1,249

Figure 5. Bootstrapped distribution of tuition fees/unit of sampled LIS graduate schools

Figure 6. Confidence interval of tuition fees/unit of sampled LIS graduate schools

The responses from other LIS schools, those that are outside the UP System, indicate that the lowest tuition fee per unit that is currently being charged to prospective students stands at Php 300, while the highest tuition fee per unit that is currently being charged, stands at Php 1,979. Data indicates as well that miscellaneous fees charged to prospective students range between Php 590 to Php 9,514. The rationale for these fees follow the same rationale posited by UP Diliman graduate programs—the need for technological advancement and improvement in the facilities.

Table 2
Survey Questionnaire Responses from LIS Schools Graduate Programs

School	Total units	Tuition fee/ Unit	Misc fees	Added fees	Enrollees per sem	Tuition last updated since	Factors in deciding the program's cost
Cor Jesu College, Inc.	39	600	4835.72	N/A	10-12	2018	Conducted consultation from our stakeholders like the parents, etc. and the finance department will do the computation; another for the percentage of the increase; the IA and finance office will submit the agreed amount to CHED for approval.
Negros Oriental State University	36	600	800	-	5	-	Required students to pay a partial of 2,000 upon enrollment. The remaining balance will be settled at the end of the semester, but some would settle it when they enroll for the next semester.
Saint Louis University	39	1669	9514	N/A	3	No idea	For improvement of facilities and salary of faculty
Mariano Marcos State University	39	300	590	-	2	-	Needed for Library Fee, Medical/Dental Fee, Student Body Organization Fee, Guidance Fee, Mutual Aid Fund, University Organ Fee, among others
University of Perpetual Help Laguna	42	1979	3455.5	5425	15	2018	Need for technological advancement

* Before we implement any changes/increases to our tuition and miscellaneous fees, we conducted consultation from our stakeholders like the parents, etc. and the finance department will do the computation and after that, another consultation for the percentage of the increase, after the outcome of the consultation, the IA and finance office will submit the agreed amount to CHED for approval.

** We require students to pay a partial of 2,000 upon enrollment. The remaining balance will be settled at the end of the semester, but some would settle it when they enroll for the next semester.

*** needed for Library Fee, Medical/Dental Fee, Student Body Organization Fee, Guidance Fee, Mutual Aid Fund, University Organ Fee, among others

Conclusion

Out of all findings, it can be inferred that the tuition fee for the Master in Archives and Records Management program can have its rates adjusted at less than 3,000 pesos per unit. It is recommended that future researchers have a further study on factors affecting the tuition fee rates of Library and Information Science programs being offered in the country. These can be compared and further details on similar factors having different costs can be included. On the other hand, there is a further need to evaluate the willingness-to-pay of prospective students of UP SLIS graduate programs among possible price ranges of tuition fees.

It is also important to take into consideration all factors in determining the cost of graduate course offerings mentioned by graduate school administrators both in UP Diliman and select Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering LIS graduate programs. Responses are showing that the majority of graduate schools made recent adjustments on tuition fee policies in 2018. This is reflective of the time of implementation of Republic Act 10931, known as the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act in State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) for the academic year 2017-2018. The need for technological advancement and maintenance of facilities, financial capacity of students, the need for competitive rates, and compliance with the existing university policy appear to be the driving forces in tuition fee policies of universities.

In addition, there may be a relationship between the location of each LIS graduate school, the relative standard and cost of living within the area, and the rates which are charged to prospective students. Further, there may be a connection between the privatized education structure of the highest tuition fee per unit respondent in the survey (University of Perpetual Help Laguna) and the public education structure of the lowest tuition fee per unit respondent (Mariano Marcos State University). More data on this causal relationship may provide further information as to the variation of tuition fee per unit rates between LIS schools in this study. Varying rates between LIS schools' graduate programs may also be influenced and affected by their teaching and curriculum setup. Tangible offerings and services in each HEI can be physically assessed in the future for a more grounded comparison beyond numbers.

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Appendices

Survey Questionnaire

Survey on Tuition Fee Policies of Graduate Programs Offered in UP Diliman

Link: <https://forms.gle/EBikVNP1J4vrph368>

Good day!

We are undergraduate students from the UP School of Library and Information Studies. As part of our requirements for our LIS 192 (Quantitative Research Methods in LIS) class, we are conducting a survey regarding the existing tuition rates of graduate programs offered in UP Diliman and in Philippine Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering LIS courses.

We would like to humbly request for a few minutes of your time to answer this form for our final project. The results will be used to assess the pricing of the newly-instituted Master in Archives and Records Management. More details about MARM here: www.upslis.info.

All data collected will remain confidential. If you have any questions or concerns, you may email our contact person Joseph Icaonapo at jgicaonapo@up.edu.ph and/or research adviser Dan Anthony Dorado at dddorado@up.edu.ph.

Thank you very much and stay safe!

Under the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or RA 10173, all information collected will be used only for the mentioned purposes and accessible only to the researchers. By granting consent, you agree to the collection and processing of all the data that you have disclosed in this survey.

I. Course Information

Graduate Degree Program/s Offered

How many units are required to complete the program in total?

College Email Address

Contact Number

Facebook/Social Media Accounts

II. Tuition Fee Policy Information

How much does it cost to take the program per unit?

How much are the miscellaneous fees per semester?

How much are the additional/other required fees per semester?

When was the last time the college administration updated the tuition fee policy for your graduate school program/s?

Can you share with us some of the factors involved in deciding how much should be charged to prospective students of your college's graduate program/s?

Can you share with us how many graduate school students you have each semester on average?

Kindly upload pertinent files with information about your school's tuition fee if there is any. If the information can be found online, kindly indicate the link of the website below.

Survey on Tuition Fee Policies of Graduate Programs in HEIs Offering Library and Information Science Courses

Link: <https://forms.gle/CtvCbZyPUH9YrVpE9>

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